

Investigating the Influence of Culture Conditions on Antimicrobial Activity of NC01 Strain

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Abstract

Myxococcus sp. is an important large genus in the family of myxobacteria because it is considered a prospecting source of secondary metabolites. This study aims to: (i) Identify potential NC01 strain by morphological, biochemical and 16S rDNA gene sequences; (ii) Evaluate antimicrobial activity by agar well-diffusion and microdilution methods; (iii) Survey medium and fermentation conditions that exhibit the best antimicrobial activity and (iv) Determine active fractionation by thin-layer chromatography (TLC) bioautography. The results show that the NC01 strain was designated *Myxococcus fulvus*. This strain demonstrated inhibition in 9/10 of the strains tested with the most impressive activity being recorded on MSSA, *A. niger* and *Penicillium* sp. with a minimum inhibitory concentration of 1 µg/mL however this strain did not show inhibition of *E. coli*. The survey of fermentation conditions revealed the crude extract exhibited the best antimicrobial activity on medium P at pH 7.2, temperature 37 °C. The two segments No. 2 and No. 3 (Rf = 0.23 and Rf = 0.28) contain compounds that were active on *A. niger*.

Introduction

Myxobacteria were known to be Gram-negative bacteria that exist commonly in soil, water, and the feces of wild animals such as rabbits or sheep with complex multicellular lifestyles, exhibiting multifaceted and highly sophisticated cooperative behaviors [1]. During development, Myxobacteria can grow as a saprophytic bacterium by decomposing polymers in nature or lysing down a variety of microorganisms that help keep a competitive advantage in the biome. As a result, they play a significant role in nature through controlling microorganisms in the soil or decomposing dead microorganisms [2]. Moreover, Myxobacteria are considered a new source of medications for drug development studies. They present opportunities to study active ingredients derived from microorganisms because they have produced more than 100 secondary metabolites and 600 new derivatives with unique structures and functions that are difficult to find in other bacteria. Those derivatives account for 47% of anticancer drugs and 70% of anti-infective drugs [3], [4]. *Myxococcus* sp. is a large genus of great interest to researchers because most secondary metabolites found in this genus are new substances with diverse

biological activities, especially *Myxococcus xanthus* and *Myxococcus fulvus*.

M. fulvus is also one of the most commonly isolated species in decaying soil, wood, or bark in the genus *Myxococcus* [5]. In a nutrient-rich environment, vegetative cells combine to move by sliding on the surface of the environment called ripples to hunt and form spreading colonies known as swarms. When the nutrient source is depleted, the cells will gather together to form a spherical, yellow fruit body containing spores (myxospore) that help resist adverse environmental influences. Meanwhile, peripheral cells located on the outside of the fruiting body continue to search for nutrients. When encountering a nutrient-rich environment, even at low levels, the spores will germinate and develop new vegetative cells [6]. So far, scientists have isolated many potential active ingredients from this species such as: KYC4048 (anti-cancer) [7], myxopyronin (anti-bacterial) [8], myxothiazol (anti-fungal) [9]....

Although many biocompounds have been isolated and published, genomic analyses showed that mycobacteria are ability of producing more bioactive substances than published figures [10]. The approach

More Information

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to bioactive screening, then fractionation and purification of compounds is an important strategy in the discovery of secondary metabolites [11]. This study conducted morphological characterization, biochemical tests, and 16S rDNA gene sequencing to identify the NC01 strain. Next, the influence of certain conditions and fermentation medium were investigated to obtain the most bioactive extract. This extract used to identify the segment containing the active compound. That helps guide the isolation and purification of the pure active constituent.

Materials and Methods

Materials

NC01 strain is provided by the Department of Microbiology – Parasitology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Nguyen Tat Thanh University.

Identification

Morphological Identification

The NC01 strain was activated and cultured on VY2 (w/v, baker's yeast 0.5%; CaCl₂.2H₂O 0.1%; vitamin B12 0.5 mg/L; agar 1.5%; pH 7.2) at room temperature. After 7 days, the characteristics of the fruit body and the cluster was observed under a microscope and described. Gram staining to observe the characteristics of vegetative cells and myxospores under optical microscopy. The data was compared with published documents for preliminary identification [12], [13].

Biochemical Test Identification

Catalase Test: a drop of 3% H₂O₂ solution was added to the colony, when air bubbles appear for 30 seconds, there has been a positive reaction [14], [15].

Urease test: the bacteria was transplanted into a Christensen (w/v, pepton 0.1%, NaCl 0.5%, glucose 0.1%, phenol red 0.0012%, KH₂PO₄ 0.2%, agar 1.5%, pH 6.8-6.9) urea-supplemented medium and incubated for 7 days. Positive reaction when pink appears [14], [16].

Starch Hydrolysis Test: the experimental bacteria cultured on containing the basic medium of the starch hydrolysis test (w/v, starch solution 1.0%, K₂HPO₄ 0.03%, MgCO₃ 0.1%, NaCl 0.05%, KNO₃ 0.1%, agar 1.5%, pH 7.2-7.4) at room temperature for 7-14 days. After the bacteria grew, Lugol reagent was given, the hydrolysis of starch created a colorless area around the colony [14], [15].

Casein Hydrolysis Test: the bacteria was inoculated on casein agar (w/v, TSA 4%, skim milk 1.3%) at 30-35 °C for 7-14 days. The TCA 35% solution was added, the hydrolysis of the casein created a colorless area around the colony [14], [17].

Cellulose Hydrolysis Test: the basic medium containing cellulose (w/v, yeast extract 0.1%, CMC 1.0%, K₂HPO₄ 0.2%, MgSO₄.7H₂O 0.03%, (NH₄)₂SO₄ 0.25%, Congo red 0.1%, agar 1.5%) was prepared. The bacteria cultured and incubated for 7 to 14 days. The congo red dye (1 mg/ml) was applied for 10-15 minutes, then washed with NaCl 1M 2-3 times (every 15 minutes).

Hydrolysis of cellulose made a transparent ring around the bacterial cluster [14], [18].

Testing with the ZYM API Kit: the ZYM API (Biomerieux) kit was used to conduct biochemical testing, the results were read based on the manufacturer's instructions [19].

16S rDNA Gene Sequencing

DNA was extracted using the Genomic DNA Extraction Kit (ABT, Vietnam) conformity with the manufacturer's instructions. The DNA was amplified with primer pairs 27F and 1492R. PCR products were transmitted for sequencing at Axil Scientific Pte Ltd, Singapore. The genome sequence was assembled using the Lasergene program, the Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) on NCBI was used to analyze nucleotide sequences and phylogenetic trees were built with MEGA software version 11 [20].

Fermentation of Crude Extract

Fermentation of NC01 strain in 100 mL P medium (w/v, peptone 0.2%; starch solution 0.8%; baker's yeast 0.4%; yeast extract 0.2%; CaCl₂.2H₂O 0.1%; MgSO₄.7H₂O 0.4%; Hepes 100 mM; EDTA-Fe 0.0008%; pH 7.2) was supplemented with 1-2% Amberlite XAD-16N resin for 14 days at room temperature, shaking 180 rpm [19]. After the fermentation process, the resin was collected and eluted with acetone and methanol, respectively. The extraction solution was merged, and volatilized under low pressure to acquire the crude extract.

Evaluation of Antimicrobial Activity

Conducting trials on 10 strains of microorganisms including 3 Gram-positive strains: MSSA (ATCC 25923), MRSA (ATCC 43300), *Streptococcus faecalis* (ATCC 29212); 2 Gram-negative strains: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC 27853), *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922); 4 strains of fibrous fungi: *Aspergillus niger* (ATCC 16404), *Penicillium* sp., *Mucor* sp., *Rhizopus* sp. and yeast *Candida albicans* (ATCC 10231) provided by the Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Medicine and Pharmacy at Ho Chi Minh City.

Evaluation of Antimicrobial Activity by Diffusion Well Method

The method was conducted on MHA (Muller-Hinton agar, MHA with 2% glucose supplementation and methylene blue for *C. albicans*). 75 µL of crude extract is added to each wells. Incubate at 35-37°C for 24-48 hours, recording the inhibition ring diameter [21].

Determination of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

The microdilution method was carried out according to the instructions of CLSI [21] on Muller-Hinton broth (MHB, MHB adds 2% glucose to *C. albicans*). 30 µl of resazurin reagent (0.015%) was added to the wells to indicate growth. The results were read after 16-48 hours of incubation. Negative symptoms are 10% DMSO and positive symptoms include amikacin and gentamycin, amphotericin B and fluconazole.

Survey of the medium and fermentation conditions

Fermentation Medium Survey

The NC01 strains were fermented in different environments CTT (w/v, casiton 1%; MgSO4 8.0 mM; KH2PO4 1.0 mM; Tris-HCl 10.0 mM; pH 7.6), CYE (w/v, casitone 1%; yeast extract 0.5%; MgSO4.7H2O 1,0; HEPES 50 mM; pH 7.6), MD1 (w/v, pepton 0.%; MgSO4.7H2O 0.2%; CaCl2.2H2O 0.7%; vitamine B12 0.5 mg/L; pH 7.2), SSG (w/v, potato starch 0.8%; soybean meal residue 0.3%; glucose 0.2%; yeast extract 0.15%; MgSO4.7H2O 0.1%; CaCl2.2H2O 0.1; EDTA - Na - Fe (III) 0.0008%; pH 7.2), and P [12].

Survey of Fermentation Conditions

The factors surveyed included the temperature (25, 30, 37 and 40 °C) and pH (6.0; 7.2; 8.0 and 9.0) of the culture medium.

Determination of Active Segments by TLC Bioautography

Quantitative dotted 10 µL of high extraction onto a thin sheet of silica gel 60 F254 and chromatographic development with the dynamic phase of ethyl acetate: n-hexane (7:3). Place the TLC on MHA medium that had been tested with microorganisms, left at 5-8 °C for 8 hours and then incubated under appropriate

conditions. The diameter of the inhibition zone was recorded after 16-48 hours.

Technical Information

This study was conducted to achieve the following objectives. First, identify potential NC01 strain by morphological, biochemical and 16S rDNA gene sequences. Second, evaluate antimicrobial activity by agar well-diffusion and microdilution methods. Third, survey medium and fermentation conditions that exhibit the best antimicrobial activity and determine active fractionation by thin-layer chromatography (TLC) bioautography.

Results

Identification

After 7 days of culture, the NC01 strain formed swarm with a diameter of 5-6 cm on the surface of the medium in a spiral shape, creating yellow diffuse pigment. The fruit body was spherical or oval, light orange, located individually. After Gram staining, it was observed that the vegetative cells were pink, 3-6 µm long, tapered, and spherical myxospores. At the same time, on the WCX medium, NC01 cells gradually slid towards *E. coli* bacteria and lyse them to be used as food and form fruit bodies (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Morphology and Sliding Motion of the NC01 Strain (A: swarm, B: fruit body, C: vegetative cell, D: myxospore, E: sliding motion)

The results of substrate metabolism are presented in Table 1.

The 16S rDNA sequence data was sent to the Genbank with the code ON055770, after the analysis showed a 100% similarity to the species *Myxococcus fulvus*.

Morphological comparison according to The Prokaryotes [12] and Bergey's Manual of Systematic Bacteriology [13], sliding motion and bacterial lysis combined with 16S rDNA sequence analysis showed similarity to *M. fulvus*.

Table 1. Biochemical Test Results of NC01 Strain

STT	Enzym	Result	STT	Enzym	Result
	Catalase	+		Starch Hydrolysis	-
	Urease	+		Cellulose Hydrolysis	-
	Casein Hydrolysis	+			
Kit API ZYM					
1	Control		11	Acid phosphatase	+
2	Alkaline Phosphatase	+	12	Naphthol-AS-BI phosphohydrolase	+
3	Esterase (C4)	+	13	α-galactosidase	-
4	Esterase lipase (C8)	+	14	β-galactosidase	-
5	Lipase (C14)	+	15	β-glucuronidase	-
6	Leucine arylamidase	-	16	α-glucosidase	-
7	Valine arylamidase	-	17	β-glucosidase	-
8	Cystine arylamidase	+	18	N-acetyl-β-glucosaminidase	-
9	Trypsine	-	19	α-mannosidase	-
10	α-chymotrypsine	-	20	α-fucosidase	-

Note: (+) positive, (-) negative

Figure 2: Phylogenetic Plants of NC01 Strain

Evaluation of Antimicrobial Activity

The crude extract of the NC01 strain showed activity on 10 tested microbial strains with resistance ring diameters ranging from 12-69 mm. Antifungal activity

(resistance ring diameter 23-69 mm) is better than antibacterial activity (12-26 mm). Specifically, the best activity on *A. niger* with a resistance ring diameter of 69 mm and the lowest is 12 mm for *E. coli* (Table 2).

Table 2: Microbial Resistance Ring Diameter of NC01 Strain

Test Substance	Resistance Ring Diameter (mm)									
	MSSA	MRSA	<i>S. faecalis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>Rhizopus sp.</i>	<i>Mucor sp.</i>	<i>Penicillium sp.</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
Crude extract	26,0 ± 0,0	19,7 ± 0,5	17,0 ± 0,0	11,3 ± 0,5	15,0 ± 0,0	25,0 ± 0,00	26,3 ± 0,9	27,2 ± 0,24	68,3 ± 0,5	67,7 ± 0,9
Amikacin	20,0 ± 0,0	22,3 ± 0,5	20,3 ± 0,5	19,7 ± 0,5	25,0 ± 0,5					
Gentamycin	19,7 ± 0,5	17,0 ± 0,8	18,3 ± 0,5	15,7 ± 0,5	24,7 ± 0,5					
Amphotericin B						28,0 ± 0,0	25,7 ± 0,5	19,0 ± 0,0	19,3 ± 0,5	25,7 ± 0,5
Fluconazole						30,0 ± 0,0				
DMSO 10%	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Note: (-) negative

The crude extract demonstrated activity on Gram-positive bacteria including MSSA, MRSA, *S. faecalis* with resistance ring diameters of 26, 20 and 17 mm, respectively, better than Gram-negative bacteria including *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa* with diameters of 12 and 15 mm.

The MIC value of the extract ranges from 1-512 µg/mL. In particular, the highest resistance activity was observed on 3 strains of MSSA, *Penicillium sp.* and *A. niger* with a MIC value of 1 µg/mL and no MIC value was determined on *E. coli* (Table 3).

Table 3: The Minimum Inhibitory Concentration of NC01 Across 10 Test Microbial Strains

Test Substance	MIC (µg/ml)									
	MSSA	MRSA	<i>S. faecalis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>Rhizopus sp.</i>	<i>Mucor sp.</i>	<i>Penicillium sp.</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
Crude extract	1	4	16	-	512	16	32	16	1	1
Amikacin	2	16	16	16	16					
Gentamycin	4	4	2	4	4					
Amphotericin B						8	1	1	0,5	0,5
Fluconazole						8				
DMSO 10%	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Note: (-) negative

Survey of the Medium and Fermentation Conditions

Fermentation Medium Survey

The crude extract showed the strongest antimicrobial activity when cultured in P medium, specifically 9 experimental microbial strains were inhibited (except *E. coli*) and MIC value ranged from 1-512 µg/mL, followed by MD1 and SSG medium showed activity on

8 experimental microbial strains but the average MIC value ranged from 64-512 µg/mL. The lowest were CTT and CYE mediums, only 3 strains of the test microorganism were inhibited at a concentration of 512 µg/mL. The results of the evaluation of antimicrobial activity from crude extracts obtained on 5 different mediums are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: MIC Values of Crude Extracts per 10 Test Microbial Strains (µg/mL)

Medium	MIC (µg/mL)									
	MSSA	MRSA	<i>S. faecalis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>Rhizopus sp.</i>	<i>Mucor sp.</i>	<i>Penicillium sp.</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
CTT	512	512	-	-	-	-	-	-	512	-
CYE	512	512	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
MD1	512	512	512	-	-	256	512	256	128	128
SSG	512	512	512	-	-	512	-	512	64	128
P	1	4	16	-	512	16	32	16	1	1

Note: (-) negative

Survey of Fermentation Conditions

Optimization of fermentation conditions is carried out with the optimum environment P and changes in the pH

factor and fermentation temperature. The optimal fermentation condition for the NC01 strain is pH 7.2; 37°C. The particular results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Results of the fermentation conditions survey

Factor		MIC (µg/mL)									
		MSSA	MRSA	<i>S. faecalis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>Rhizopus sp.</i>	<i>Mucor sp.</i>	<i>Penicillium sp.</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
pH	6,0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	7,2	1	4	16	-	512	16	32	16	1	1
	8,0	64	64	256	-	-	128	512	64	32	32
	9,0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Temperature (°C)	25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	30	128	128	256	-	-	2	512	128	64	32
	37	1	4	16	-	512	1	32	16	1	1
	40	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Note: (-) negative

The microdilution method was used to determine the MIC value of the extracts from different fermentation environments and conditions, the results show that fermentation in P environment at 37 °C, pH 7.2 is the most optimal. This condition is applied to ferment the crude extract from the NC01 strain and is carried out subsequent testing.

Determination of Active Segments by TLC Bioautography

Chromatographic development was carried out by ethyl acetate dynamic phase: n-hexane = 7:3, on the chromatography 8 traces appeared. TLC bioautography have identified 2 antimicrobial segments, segment 2 ($R_f = 0.23$) and segment 3 ($R_f = 0.28$), showing activity on *A. niger* with an antifungal ring diameter of 21 mm (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Results of TLC Bioautography of NC01 Extract on *Aspergillus niger*

Discussion

General features such as the color and shape of the fruiting bodies were principal in the initial identification of the NC01 strain, however they could not help to accurately identify at the species level due to the many similarities between *Myxococcus* sp. species. Therefore, it is necessary to combine with the biochemical characteristics and sequencing of the 16S rDNA gene. The results of biochemical tests of the NC01 strains in the study are similar to those of R. Thaxter in 1892 or in the description of 15 genera of the Myxococcaceae family by R. Garcia in 2014 [14]. In addition, there is not much data on the biochemical characteristics of *Myxococcus* sp. in particular and Myxobacteria in general published in previous studies. Therefore, using the ZYM API kit of 19 biochemical tests carried out has contributed to providing more biochemical data of *Myxococcus* sp., which is the basis

for identifying *Myxococcus* sp. with more accurate biochemical tests.

When determining the antimicrobial activity of crude extract, antifungal activity (resistance ring diameter 23-69 mm) is better than antibacterial activity (12-26 mm). The result is consistent with the report of J. Diez et al. who argued that biological compounds made from antifungal Myxobacteria are better than antibacterial [22]. Moreover, activity on gram-positive bacteria is better than gram-negative. F. Gaspari et al. also conducted an antimicrobial activity survey of 62 isolated strains of *Myxococcus* sp. and 17/19 strains were active on Gram-positive bacteria with an inhibitory ring diameter greater than 14 mm and a defined MIC value from 1-512 µg/mL. In contrast, only 8/19 strains resist Gram-negative bacteria with the inhibition ring mostly in the range of 10-14 mm and the determined MIC value was 64-512 µg/mL [23]. This is similar to the results of Ivana Charousová's study [24]. P medium was identified as the optimal culture medium for the NC01 strain. Next, 2 factors of pH and ambient temperature also affect the ability of the selected potential strain to produce secondary metabolites. *Myxococcus* sp. usually grows in the pH range of 6.5-8.5, but some strains can also grow at acidic or alkaline pH [25]. For that reason, in this study, the pH

conditions between 6.0 and 10.0 were investigated. The results showed that, under neutral pH conditions (pH=7.2), the NC01 strain showed the best activity. Kathrin I. Mohr (2018) has suggested that Myxobacteria are thermophilic microorganisms and they can operate in temperatures from 4-44 °C. The scientists isolated Myxobacteria strains that grow optimally at temperatures of 24-26 °C, 30 °C (this is the optimal temperature for most strains), 35-37 °C, and 40-44 °C. This study chose 4 temperatures to survey which were 25 °C, 30 °C, 37 °C and 40 °C [25]. Through the evaluation of high activity extracted by microdilution method, the NC01 strain showed the best activity when cultured at 37 °C in accordance with the study of Kathrin I. Mohr et al. (2018) [26].

Separation by thin-layer chromatography combined with determination of the biological activity of the components contained in the extract. The detection of 2 segments only shows the growth inhibition of *A. niger*. It is possible that, after separating into small fractions, the concentration of each fraction is lower than that of the crude extract, and at the same time, the volume of the extract to dot the thin plate is very small (only 10 µl) and is adsorbed by the silica gel plate, reducing the concentration of the extract paste, so it cannot be inhibited. This is the disadvantage of the TLC bioautography method. However, with its convenience, speed, ease and economy, this method is still

commonly used in identifying biologically active segments and helping to guide the isolation of pure compounds. parts of the manuscript, such as in the Introduction or the Results section.

Conclusion

From the data collected, it was determined that NC01 is similar to *Myxococcus fulvus*. NC01 strain extract showed impressive antimicrobial activity on tested microbial strains, in which the activity on fungi was better than bacteria and Gram-positive bacteria were better than Gram-negative. The medium and fermentation condition parameters are determined. After culture under optimal conditions, the extract for 2 polarized fractions with $R_f = 0.23$ and $R_f = 0.28$ contains biologically active ingredients.

Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest

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